

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OKECHUKWU****FIRST NAME: NONYELUM****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE (PERIODS 1-5)

1. How would you view the EUCLID approach in ACA-401 course and its contents?

- The approach prepares and ensure students grounding in the fundamentals of language communications, style guides (including major variations in the two acceptable UK or US English),¹ and general academic writing by advocating for early writing, sentence planning, critical thinking on the question, and constant revision of drafts all contribute to the effective writing of essays.²**
- Gives an overview of what is expected of the students.
- Scenario planning for a successful learning in EUCLID.
- Prepares EUCLID students in standards for communicating in English language.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *How to Write a Response Paper* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 10.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 13.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Justified

Formatted: Font: Italic

2. Do you believe that EUCLID’s recommended reading titled, “How to Write a Response Paper (RP)” did achieve the aim of offering the students the prerequisites for such writing?

The text details the step-by-step guide, instructions, and examples on EUCLID’s acceptable standards for writing a response paper, which is a requisite for the completion of most periods for all courses.³

A general note on writing response papers, advancing organizing the paper into the three parts described- the summary, your reaction, and the conclusion.

A format for writing response papers, which prepares and ensure students grounding in the fundamentals of language communications, style guides, and general academic writing.

An instruction manual for writing academic papers in EUCLID.

3. State in a sentence the thrust of ACA-401D period four.

The recommended text, (“a highly practical reference for graduate students, with the goal that a student is able to produce a dissertation),⁴ prepares students “from beginning to end on the road map for starting and finishing one’s dissertation.

A hand held session guiding the students through the dissertation process.

A comprehensive overview to helpfully ensure that the researcher understands, ab initio, the necessary elements that will constitute each section of his dissertation.

Prepares EUCLID students in standards for communicating in English language.

³ [Cleenewerck](#) and [Gulma](#), *How to Write a Response Paper*, 10.

⁴ [Linda D. Bloomberg](#) and [Marie Volpe](#), *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018), 30-31.

Deleted: Cleenewerck

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Justified

4. How does one portray the process of completing a qualitative research as doable without neglecting the complexity?

Entails logical, systematic thinking that draws from one's ability to successfully master both the content and the process (no matter one's institution), by ensuring that the basic components of all dissertations -an introduction, a review of the relevant literature, a review of methodology, a presentation of findings, a presentation of analysis and interpretation, and a presentation of conclusions and recommendations – are properly covered.⁵

Turn in a dissertation.

Following the guidelines and keeping the focus on answering one's hypothetical questions.

Prepare one's research questions in line with proving the hypothesis.

5. Give an overview of period two based on the recommended reading.

The recommended text overviews "how" one could create a piecemeal of any research project and tackle them in bits at a time, to handle the unnerving task of "starting" a research project, via providing a summary of the steps and mental routines that underlie all research (wherever it's done) and of the procedures to assemble a paper, draft it, and revise it.⁶

It provides practical advice for one to formulate the right questions, read critically, and build arguments to support one's claims.

The manual is a very comprehensive tool for writing credible research, at whatever level of the graduate program.

It provides practical advice for students to formulate the right questions, read critically, and build arguments to support their claims.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 29.

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*, 13.

6. What would you surmise, from period three, as the researcher’s primary duty?

- To “get the facts right”; followed by the duty of telling his readers “where the facts came from” - tell the source of the facts so that readers can judge their reliability and check them if they wish - to wit that, the researcher must “cite the sources of the facts, ideas, or words” he used in his paper.⁷**
- Find a research topic and work on it using given guidelines by one’s institution.
- To make a claim, explain how he reached it—to ask, he has the belief.
- To justify his convictions via providing literature that echoes his narratives.

7. What clearly differentiates academic writing from the other types of writing?

- The guiding structures and frameworks of academic essays - the “process” of writing an academic or scholarly essay, which includes problem definition, resource gathering, critical thinking/reading, essay planning, and writing⁸- to provide writers with effectiveness and consistency in the presentation of their ideas in a logical, scientific, evidence-based order,⁹ clearly differentiates academic writing from the other types.**
- The structure and choice of topic.
- Critical thinking that involves a conscious application of established techniques to processing gathered information.
- Academic writing is distinct from other types in that the plan involves ordering information in a logical scientific argumentative order.

8. In defining a research project, what five guiding goals must the researcher pay heed to?

- The five guiding goals for the researcher are: ask a question worth answering from your field of interest; find an answer that you can support with good reasons: make your claim(s) or hypothesis; find good data that you can use as reliable evidence to support your reasons; draft an argument that makes a good case for your answer; and revise that draft until readers will think you met the first four goals.¹⁰**

Deleted: ¶
¶
¶

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*, 139.

Formatted: Font: Italic

⁸ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *How to Write a Response Paper*, 7-14.

Deleted: .

⁹ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*, 19.

Formatted: Font: Italic

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 23-32.

Deleted: 10 Turabian, A Manual for Writers of Research Papers

- Find resources that are available in your local library.
 - Can your research project be reflexive of your convictions?
 - Academic writing is different from other types of writing so your choice of language must be academic and reflective of acceptable standards.
9. In reviewing select and approved thesis from your course field, what would inform your assessment?

The overall quality of: the dissertation as compared with the Turabian guidelines;¹¹ abstract and structure;¹² the English language and use of references;¹³ or presence of methodology and literature review;¹⁴ argumentations;¹⁵ recommendations and conclusions;¹⁶ and bibliography.¹⁷

Deleted: O

Commented [GK1]: Replace this edition with the most recent one you were provided with!

- The arrangement and choice of topic.
- Critical thinking that involves a conscious application of established techniques to processing gathered information.
- Academic writing is distinct from other types in that the plan involves ordering information in a logical scientific argumentative order.

10. How would you rate the effectiveness of the coursepack delivery mode with regards to impact on the student's preparedness for the task ahead?

Deleted: ¶

Featuring distinct discussions and instructions, as well as relevant references to scholarly reads on the basics for the writing of international academic and professional papers; punctuation; plagiarism; rules of styles; differentiation between American and British English; Latin abbreviations and expressions, the document is tailor made for student's orientation and onboarding.¹⁸

¹¹ Ibid., (2003), 67-75.

¹² Ibid., (2018), 302-313.

¹³ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 71-74.

¹⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*, (2003), 54-66.

¹⁵ Ibid., (2018), 310-313.

¹⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 671-689.

¹⁷ Ibid., 56-58, 45-55.

¹⁸ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *How to Write a Response Paper*, 7-41.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Formatted: Font: Italic

- The Coursepack maps out EUCLID's preferred style guide for students on relevant concepts for the academic research ahead.
- A general overview of ground rules, for students to be fully equipped for academic research and the writing involved.
- Practical nuggets for students to be clear, concise, and open to others' opinions.

Deleted: ¶

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and F. Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.
- “Grammarly’s Complete Punctuation Guide”. *Punctuation: The Ultimate Guide | Grammarly*, www.grammarly.com/punctuation-test, (accessed June 23, 2023).
- “How to Use Zotero (a Complete Beginner’s Guide)”. *YouTube*, 13 Oct. 2021, www.youtube.com/watch?v=JG7Uq_JFDzE&list=PPSV.
- Pensalfini, Rob. “The Americans Are Destroying the English Language – or Are They?” *The Conversation*, 7 Jan. 2014, <https://theconversation.com/the-americans-are-destroying-the-english-language-or-are-they-21461>, (accessed February 3, 2023).
- “The Americans are ruining our Language”, *The Fifth Columnist*, 16 Feb. 2013, <https://fifthcolumnistblog.wordpress.com/2013/02/16/the-americans-are-ruining-our-language/>, (accessed February 3, 2023).
- “Turabian Documentation”, https://library.austincc.edu/help/turabian/includeturabian/turabian_docguide.pdf, (accessed June 26, 2023).
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 7th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2003.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.